

Supplementary Design and Circuit Files

Prepared for the JoVe manuscript titled “Mechanical interventions during early cardiovascular development in the avian embryo - Left Atrial Ligation Model” by Bortecine Sevgin, Merve Nur Coban, Faruk Karatas, Kerem Pekkan

Auxiliary Humidifier System Design and Construction for research grade egg incubators

Introduction and Objective

The successful development of avian embryos rely heavily on maintaining optimal temperature and humidity levels. In our cardiovascular development research, to achieve robust environmental control, industry grade egg incubators are preferred. Due to usual wear and tear, the routine use of these systems require replacement of their humidifier systems and control units. This may be costly and obtaining replacement parts may delay the ongoing research plans. Furthermore, implementing additional temperature and humidity control systems would improve the embryo yield significantly. As such, if there is an unexpected humidifier malfunction, the simpler replacement systems are needed to keep sufficient humidity levels. Therefore, an in-house designed and built auxiliary humidity control system is presented here that will fit to a wide range of egg incubators. This system can be expanded further and can be tailored towards the individual research needs.

Parts Used in the Humidifier System

The proposed humidity control circuit employs sensors, dc motors and a microprocessor as sketched in Figure 1. All parts used and their sources are listed below in Table 1. The Arduino sketch that drives these parts are also provided in this repository (File Name: TheProject.ino).

Table 1: Bill of materials used in the humidity control circuit for avian embryo egg incubators.

Component Name	No.	Source of Materials
Arduino Uno	1	https://www.arduino.cc
12V water pump IP68	1	https://www.robotshop.com/urun/12v-dc-su-pompasi-600litre-saat-5m-su-itme-gucu
Atomizing humidity maker 24V	3	https://gazikulucka.com/magaza/kulucka-ekipmanlari/kulucka-nemlendirme-cihazlari/kulucka-makinesi-nem-nozulu-isikli-24v-adaptorsuz-nemlendirme-cihazi/
Fan 40*40*10mm 12V	1	https://www.direnc.net/12v-40x40x10mm-006a-7000rpm-fan
5V 1 channel relay	3	https://www.direnc.net/5v-1-kanal-role-karti
DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor	1	https://www.direnc.net/dht11-arduino-sensor-nem-ve-sicaklik-sensoru
LCD screen 16*2	1	https://www.direnc.net/2x16-karakter-lcd-modul-ekran-turuncu-slc1602a3
Potentiometer 10k	1	https://www.direnc.net/10k-stereo-potansiyometre
24V 1A adapter	1	https://www.robolinkmarket.com/24v-1a-adaptor
24V 3A adapter	1	https://www.robolinkmarket.com/24v-3a-metal-kasa-adaptor
Jumper cables	as needed	https://www.direnc.net/40-adet-erkek-erkek-jumper-20cm
Breadboard for prototyping	1	https://www.direnc.net/tekli-breadboard

Figure 1: The Schematic of the complete circuit used as temperature and humidity control. For this project an Arduino UNO microprocessor is found to be sufficient. The sketch includes two DC motors that drive the fan and water pump. Atomizing humidifiers and relays are also illustrated. Power converter has 2 inputs from 24V 1A power supply and 2 outputs are for 12V restricted voltage value. Potentiometer is deployed to control the LCD screen brightness. DHT11 humidity sensor provides the overall triggering input to the whole system.

The Problem and Specifications:

The incubator utilized in our laboratory is a Laboratory Incubator 600 Chicken Eggs 110 Volts (Kuhl, USA). The incubator chamber has sufficient space to accommodate up to 600 eggs for incubation. A typical malfunction in the original humidifier components will result lower humidity levels than the target value. For our application, a humidity level of 60% and a temperature of 100 °F were deemed necessary for optimal egg growth. While the temperature requirement could be met easily, lack of adequate humidity would result lower number of normal developed embryos. Therefore, the primary objective of this system is to provide a humid air supply to the eggs. Additionally, it is essential to maintain good air circulation within the incubator. This air circulation is facilitated by adjustable holes present on the incubator, allowing for the exchange of air between the inside and outside of the incubator. This requires a continuous supply of humid air during the incubation.

Design:

To provide humidity to the incubator, three atomizing humidity makers are employed in this project. These support the original humidity generation system of the incubator via the air heating system. Ultrasonic atomizers can generate cold, humid air at room temperature, which is suitable for the incubator environment as well (see Figure 2 for ultrasonic atomizers used).

Figure 2: In the proposed auxiliary control unit humidity is generated using a commercially available ultrasonic atomizer device (top left) and a water pump (top right). One set of temperature and humidity sensors are placed inside the incubator (bottom). Additional sensor sets can be implemented for more uniform environmental control.

To create a humidity generator reservoir, a rectangular bucket with a capacity of 2.3 L is utilized. Atomizing humidity units are placed inside this water reservoir. However, the required water volume for incubation exceeds the capacity of the humidity generator reservoir. To address this, humidity generator reservoir is connected to a larger reservoir via supply tube (please see the supply tube in Figure 3). Additionally, a water pump is incorporated to maintain a steady supply of distilled water to the water reservoir. To prevent the water level from exceeding 1.5 L level inside the humidity generator reservoir, an additional drainage tubing

(Figure 3) is connected to release any excess water. To evenly distribute the humid air generated by the atomizing units a computer fan is employed. For larger systems the use of multiple fans is recommended. The humid air is channeled to the incubator chamber via a larger diameter tubing (Humid air transfer pipe, Figure 3).

Figure 3: Illustration of the system employed to control egg incubation. The Humidity generator reservoir and atomizing humidifiers provide the humid air, whereas supply tube and drainage tube is connected such that water is continuously available for the atomizing humidifiers. The entire unit stands on a small shelf attached to the incubator side. Shelf stands as a base for humidity generator reservoir and electronics. Humid air is channelized into incubator egg environment via humid air transfer pipe.

Figure 4: The humidity generating reservoir and its associated hardware and tubing. Fan, Ultrasonic Humidifier Units and pipes are labelled describing their function.

Electronic Circuit:

The electronic circuit is powered by two power sources of 24 Volts 1A and 24 Volts 3A ratings. As the atomizing humidity generation units are intended to operate continuously, it is directly connected to the 24V 3A power supply. On the other hand, the remaining devices including the fan, pump, and Arduino microprocessor can function with lower power ratings (12 Volts). Therefore, a power converter is incorporated to reduce the voltage from 24 Volts to 12 Volts. Relays are utilized to control the power flow to the respective devices. These relays enable the devices to be powered on and off as needed. To adjust the brightness of the LCD screen, a potentiometer is employed, providing a means to regulate the screen's brightness. The way power and signals are being distributed is illustrated in Figure 5. The humidity sensor is being powered by the Arduino-uno itself due to its low energy need.

DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor is used to measure the humidity level inside the incubator (Figure 2) and the Arduino processes the signals from the sensors which triggers all other components. According to the humidity level water pump, atomizing humidifiers and fan is being triggered. First, water pump fills the humidity generator reservoir and then atomizing humidifiers create the humid air. Fan is working simultaneously with the atomizing humidifiers.

Figure 5: Assembly diagram of power supply and electrical parts. Two different power supplies have been utilized to control devices separately and to provide enough power to each device.

Operation:

The first prototype of this Auxiliary system is shown in Figure 6. The product just able to reach the target 60% humidity level. If higher humidity levels are desired several potential improvements are suggested and listed below.

Figure 6: Result of this project when it fully operates in the lab environment.

- 1) Incorporating a Water Level Switch for the Water Pump: While the atomizing humidifier has a protective mechanism to shut off when the water level is below a certain threshold, the water pump lacks this feature. To prevent damage to the water pump, an external water level switch can be connected.
- 2) Introducing a digital potentiometer connected serially to the fan would enable more precise control over the fan speed. This would provide flexibility in adjusting the airflow and optimizing the humidity distribution within the incubator.
- 3) Scaling Up the System with Multiple Atomizing Humidifiers: Currently, the project utilizes 3 atomizing humidifiers. By increasing the number of humidifiers, different humidity levels can be achieved simultaneously. However, for the purposes of this project, a gradual humidity increase is desired, so only 3 humidifiers are employed. Additional humidifiers can be controlled programmatically to attain specific humidity requirements.
- 4) Incorporation of multiple sensors sets and use of a PID control algorithm.
- 5) Converting this prototype in to a custom PCB printed board.